

Tracker - A Novel Approach for Location Tracking System using Seeker

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Abstract— Location tracking is a technology to physically locate and track people, their social media profiles and their daily activities. Seeker is employed to seek out the accurate location of the victim alongside with the device information. Nowadays, webcams are most generally in use which feeds a picture or video in real-time using the webcam. Here we are using SayCheese combined with Seeker so as to access the webcam of the victim. Attackers can integrate both links and track the location and can hack the webcam. Whenever a victim clicks on the link, the locations are going to be shown and webcam will start capturing pictures without the victim's knowledge.

Keywords—location tracking, webcam hacking, Ngrok, fatURL.

I. INTRODUCTION

With rapid development of mobile technology, it's getting easier to locate or track people with the internet. It's used for various purposes like, tracking the workers, identifying the culprit etc. Seeker is a location tracking tool that work best with smartphones. Tracking or detecting the location of vehicle is one among the important benefits. Seeker Hosts a fake website on In Built PHP Server and uses Serveo to get a link which can forward to the target. It provides accurate information's like latitude, longitude, direction, when the target is moving etc. It also provides device information like OS and public ip address of the target etc. Seeker use GPS hardware present within the device. Even if GPS is not present, like on a laptop, it fallbacks to IP Geolocation or it'll search for Cached Coordinates. If a user accepts the location permission, it will show an accurate dimension and the accuracy depends on the device.

1.1 Kali Linux.

Kali Linux is a free Debian based Linux distribution used for penetration testing and digital forensics. It includes hundreds of penetration testing tools. Kali Linux also provide way for security research based on different tools.

1.2 Ngrok

Ngrok creates a secure tunnel on the local machine along with a public URL. By default, ngrok creates both http and https end points. In the proposed system, ngrok is used to create links for both location tracking and webcam hacking.

1.3 FatURL

The link generated using seeker and saycheese are integrated using fatURL. This will generate a single link which is used to send to the victim. When the victim clicks, it will open two windows, one asks for location permission and other will start capturing pictures.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

[1] Refers, penetration testing is a series of activities undertaken to identify and exploit security vulnerabilities. It mainly includes 3 phases, test preparation, test and test analysis.

[2] Introduced an idea about what location tracking refers to technologies that physically locate and electronically record and track the movement of people or object. And also gives an idea about how location tracking is used.

[3] Depicts an idea about different methods that a mobile phone gets tracked. A combined method for tracking the location of moving devices accurately and effectively even though GPS signals was not available.

[4] Provide information about basic hacking attacks, methods and how all these are done. Deals with different type of hacking, types of hacking tools and used by hackers.

[5] Shows privacy issues in allowing location permission. Here it provides different technology that support useful location-based services (LBS), which tailor their functionality to a user's current location, privacy, might seriously hamper user acceptance.

III. SEEKER

Seeker is used to track live location of individuals by hosting a fake webpage that will ask for location permission from the victim. Seeker provide the accurate latitude, longitude, direction etc. and it also provide complete device information like operating system, public IP address etc. It grabs latitude and longitude using GPS Hardware present in the system. Also provide a google map overview to track.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The system implements seeker and saycheese together. Seeker is used to locate victim with high accuracy. It also provides the complete device information of the victim. Saycheese is used to hack the webcam in order to have a complete access to the surroundings at the same time. Both the links of seeker and saycheese are linked using fatURL that will provide a single link to the victim through a web page. When ever needed, the victim can click on the link that will show the entire details of the victim like accurate location, images etc.

Applications:

- women safety.
- School bus tracking.
- Missing cases.

Advantages:

- Can use same link for multiple persons.
- Highly accurate.
- Easily access device information.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed system include location tracking along with hacking of webcam of the victim. This is done by installing seeker for location tracking and saycheese for webcam hacking, when clicked, provide an accurate location as outcome. Installation process of both include several steps as follows;

1. Installation of Seeker:

Seeker is installed by cloning it from GitHub repository using the following commands.

- Git clone <https://github.com/thewhiteh4t/seeker.git>
- After cloning navigate to the directory.

- Set cd seeker.
- Script execution permission: `chmod 777 install.sh`
- `./install.sh`

The installation process of seeker includes,

- Python 3
- Php
- SSH
- Requests.

After completing the installation,

Step 1: `python3 seeker.py`

Fig 1: Running Seeker

- Provide the version of tool
- Check for updates.
- Start tunnel services manually.

Step 2: `./ngrok http 8080` in a new terminal.

Fig 2: Ngrok

- Provide ngrok version
- Region
- Two forwarding links and connections.

Step 3: <https://25f97f67.ngrok.io/nearyou/>

Fig 3: Location in Google map

Copy one of the forwarding links which starts with https and append /nearyou/ to this tunnel URL. Paste it on the browser. It generates a fake web interface which will show a continue button which ask for location permission of the victim. When the victim grant the permission, location information including longitude, latitude etc. and complete device information are tracked. This will automatically generate a series of numbers, when pasted on a browser will provide live location of the victim on google map.

2. Installation of Saycheese

Saycheese is installed by cloning it from GitHub.

- Gitclone
<http://github.com/thelinuxchoice/saycheese>
- Set cd saycheese.

After cloning,

Step 1: bash saycheese.sh.

```

File Edit View Search Terminal Help
root@kali:~# cd Desktop
root@kali:~/Desktop# cd saycheese
root@kali:~/Desktop/saycheese# bash saycheese.sh

Saycheese
v1.0 coded by github.com/thelinuxchoice/saycheese

[01] Serveo.net
[02] Ngrok
[+] Choose a Port Forwarding option: 02
[+] Starting php server...
[+] Starting ngrok server...
[*] Direct link: https://a3bea66d.ngrok.io
[*] Waiting targets, Press Ctrl + C to exit...
[+] Target opened the link!
[+] IP: 2409:4073:a:160b:9eee:53d2:2379:195f

```

Fig 4: Running Saycheese

- Ask for port forwarding options like ngrok and serveo.net.

Step 2: Select ngrok as port forwarding option.

- Now a direct link will be generated.

Step 3: Open the link using a browser.

Step 4: Ask for Webcam access permission.

- Webcam will start capturing images.
- All the captured images will get stored in the saycheese folder.
- It will continue until the browser is closed.

Both the links, generated using seeker and saycheese are integrated using fatURL which helps to combine 2 or more links into a single link. When the link is combined, it is supposed to send to the victim. When clicked, it helps to find the location of people in dangerous situations and automatically capture the images of the victim until the tab is closed. So, this method can be implemented as a measure of women safety. The link can be embedded in a button inside a web page. When ever the button is clicked, the location and images are shared, which will help the authority to track and locate the victim.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

Seeker and saycheese together provide many features to track victim. It should also provide distance between the victim and authority, direction of movement of the victim in order to provide a better security.

VII. CONCLUSION

Seeker utilizes html, php, JavaScript etc. to grab device information geo location with high accuracy. It is a tool which work best in smartphones. Even if the GPS hardware is not present, it'll locate the victim using cached coordinates. Alongside seeker, Saycheese is employed to hack the webcam of the victim which capture the pictures of the victim automatically. This may provide a further benefit for safety measures. This mechanism will help in many sectors like women safety, which help to trace them and capture pictures of their surroundings once they are in trouble.

VIII. REFERENCES

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